

Headline

Use it or lose it: why human knowledge can vanish — and how that matters now

Standfirst

We tend to imagine knowledge as something that only accumulates. But new research on Neanderthal fire use suggests that cultural skills can disappear — even when they are useful.

Article body

We live in a polarised world. Either we embrace a celebration of cultural grandeur, the glitter of “progress” (even written in the Brazilian flag), and the perception that great culture must endure and propagate as a kind of manifested destiny — or we lament a glorious “golden” past, lost in the ashes, compared to a bleak contemporary society.

So, on one hand we tend to assume that knowledge accumulates over time. On the other, there are fears of a post-literacy society, cultural decline, and doomsday cults — even among the rich and powerful — while a looming social collapse and the end of civilisation is never too far away, condemning us to dark ages where our fancy toys and modern medicine will be obliterated.

Surely there must be some middle ground that captures the dynamics of loss, but also what makes retention possible in a culturally rich landscape. It is time we crack the dynamics that underlie cultural loss — and its counterpart, cultural retention.

This is especially relevant because we are inhabiting a world experiencing climatic transition, where our relatively mild and predictable ten millennia of stable climate form the Holocene might vanish in the next few centuries, shifting Earth into a new era — the Anthropocene.

Cultural loss dynamics as an academic field

In the academic literature, there is a glaring omission: a targeted understanding — theorising, modelling, measurement, statistical tests and analysis — of the dynamics driving cultural loss.

Cultural loss is a broad term, ranging from the global cultural diversity of human and non-human species alike

([Andersson & Czárán 2023](https://royalsocietypublishing.org/rstb/article/378/1872/20210416/109118/The-transition-from-animal-to-human-culture)), to specific micro-trends like babies’ names, and everything in between: languages, music, identity, symbols, technology, art, religion, science, philosophy and beauty.

Given this broad blanket for “cultural loss”, we can focus on specific “practices”

([Arinyo-i-Prats, LaTosky & Turner 2025](https://ethnobiologyletters.ethnobiology.org/index.php/ebl/article/view/1896)) —

discrete cultural packages that leave measurable and identifiable records, either in people's memories or in the archaeological record.

Our new research tracks cultural loss as a fundamental feature of cultural and behavioural adaptation, crucial to understanding how our world works — one that can reshape technological histories and transform how we think about population dynamics.

Challenging a basic assumption about the retention of “useful arts”

At the core of most academic thinking about technology — in archaeology, anthropology and cultural evolution — is a simple assumption: once a useful technology emerges, it spreads and is permanently retained

([Rivers 1912](https://archive.org/details/disappearanceofu00riveiala);

[Mesoudi & Thornton 2018](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29899071/)).

We challenge this.

One of the archetypes of what it means to be human is the capacity for fire use (though [hawks in Australia](https://doi.org/10.2993/0278-0771-37.4.700) may also use it).

Other practices, like tool production, agriculture and writing, are typically treated as unidirectional achievements in human progress — things that cannot be lost.

In our recent paper,

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[Use it or lose it: a model-based assessment of the hypothesis that European Neanderthals](https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/articles/5-205/v2)

[relied on wildfires to create their campfires](https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/articles/5-205/v2)

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we model the dynamics of fire use being lost. This suggests that our basic assumptions about humans, culture and evolution need to be reassessed.

Neanderthals and campfires

One of the puzzles in the archaeological record comes from European Neanderthal sites. During the cold, dry phases of the Pleistocene, evidence for habitual campfire making seems to fade from certain regions — even though these were precisely the conditions under which fire would have been most valuable

([Abdolahzadeh et al. 2022](https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12520-022-01520-5)).

Rather than assuming Neanderthals either knew how to make fire or did not, we propose another explanation: perhaps the fire-use skill was lost when environmental fluctuations in fire availability pushed cultural retention past a tipping point, despite the advantage fire offered in cold and dry conditions.

Using model-based analysis informed by archaeological evidence, we show how fire-use skills can fade when populations go long periods without gathering embers from wildfires.

When opportunities to practise the skill are highly variable, the practice itself degrades until nobody in a group retains it, even if it survives in memory.

Fire loss can be irreversible under certain conditions. If no one retains the skill to create and maintain fire, it cannot be recovered by social learning alone. In our model, fluctuating numbers of experts eventually lead to total loss of the skill once no experts remain.

This mechanism helps explain gaps in the archaeological record. It complicates simple assumptions about the spread and persistence of technologies, and allows us to treat absence of evidence as possible evidence of absence.

How loss has been overlooked

Part of the reason cultural loss is neglected in research is that scholars tend to focus on transmission rather than on intragenerational practice and use. Only one field study has measured collective loss of ethnobotanical knowledge over a nine-year period ([Reyes-García et al. 2013](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24277979/)), while other research infers collective forgetting from digital attention data ([Candia et al. 2019](https://www.nature.com/articles/s41562-018-0474-4)).

Practice matters. Skills survive not just because they are transmitted, but because they are repeated, taught, reinforced and enacted. Without practice, expertise decays at both individual and community levels ([Arthur & Day 2019](https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198795872.013.47)).

In this sense, performance and use are the basis for retention, ahead of transmission. Without these dynamics, the durability — and fragility — of cultural knowledge disappears from view.

Lessons for archaeology and cultural evolution

The implications of our work extend far beyond Neanderthals. Cultural loss provides an explanation for gaps in the archaeological record and shows that culture is fragile and dynamic. Loss is not an anomaly explained only by collapses or “dark ages”, but a regular outcome of cultural processes.

Our findings also resonate with research on cultural keystone practices. In a companion paper,

[Rethinking Cultural Keystone Practices: Conflict Resolution Practices as Examples of Salience and Well-Being](https://ethnobiologyletters.ethnobiology.org/index.php/eb1/article/view/1896)

we argue that while all practices are governed by similar dynamics, some are more central or resilient than others, and their loss can have outsized consequences.

Looking ahead: connectivity, affordances and sudden losses

Future research needs to explore how communities maintain cultural knowledge in the face of disruption. Important factors include connectivity between groups, the accessibility of practices, and the sudden loss of experts who carry specialised knowledge.

Understanding not just how culture is transmitted, but how it is practised and maintained, will be crucial to understanding human history — and perhaps to safeguarding cultural diversity in a rapidly changing world.

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Disclosure statement

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Suggested images

Lead image:

Caption: Evidence discontinuation of campfire use in several sites in Western Europe across three climatic periods..

Figure:

Caption: Model simulation showing how fire-use expertise can recover and then decay. showing a time series of collection of embers from wildfires (red spike) which recovers the experts population. When the number of experts decays until non remains, the practice is lost.

Bibliography

1. Andersson, C. & Czárán, T. The transition from animal to human culture—simulating the social protocell hypothesis. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* **378**, 20210416 (2023).
2. Arinyo-i-Prats, A., LaTosky, S. & Turner, N. J. Rethinking Cultural Keystone Practices: Conflict Resolution Practices as Examples of Salience and Well-Being. *Ethnobiol. Lett.* **16**, 7–19 (2025).
3. Rivers, W. H. The disappearance of useful arts. *Festskr. Tillagnad Edvard Westermarck* <https://archive.org/details/disappearanceofu00riveiala> (1912).
4. Mesoudi, A. & Thornton, A. What is cumulative cultural evolution? *Proc. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* **285**, 20180712 (2018).
5. Bonta, M. *et al.* Intentional fire-spreading by “Firehawk” raptors in Northern Australia. *J. Ethnobiol.* **37**, 700–718 (2017).

6. Arinyo-i-Prats, A., Sandgathe, D., Riede, F. & Collard, M. Use it or lose it: A model-based assessment of the hypothesis that European Neanderthals relied on wildfires to create their campfires. *Open Res. Eur.* 205 (2025)
doi:<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.20477.2>.
7. Abdolazadeh, A. *et al.* Investigating variability in the frequency of fire use in the archaeological record of Late Pleistocene Europe. *Archaeol. Anthropol. Sci.* **14**, (2022).
8. Reyes-García, V. *et al.* Evidence of traditional knowledge loss among a contemporary indigenous society. *Evol. Hum. Behav.* **34**, 249–257 (2013).
9. Candia, C., Jara-Figueroa, C., Rodriguez-Sickert, C., Barabási, A.-L. & Hidalgo, C. A. The universal decay of collective memory and attention. *Nat. Hum. Behav.* **3**, 82–91 (2019).
10. Arthur, W. & Day, E. A. Skill decay: The science and practice of mitigating skill loss and enhancing retention. in *The Oxford Handbook of Expertise* (eds Ward, P., Maarten Schraagen, J., Gore, J. & Roth, E. M.) 0 (Oxford University Press, 2019).
doi:[10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198795872.013.47](https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780198795872.013.47).